

Subject: Seeking Participants for Research on Facebook Matrimonial Group Experiences

Hello [Name/Group Members]!

I am conducting my thesis research titled "Security & privacy perceptions of Pakistani Facebook matrimony group users" at Paderborn University on the experiences of individuals looking for marriage proposals on Facebook matrimonial groups. If you have encountered any negative experiences while searching for a proposal for yourself or someone else, or if you are a parent seeking a match for your children, I would love to hear from you.

Interview Details:

Format: Non-technical, open conversation.

Language Options: Conducted in either Urdu or English, as per your preference.

Confidentiality: Your privacy will be fully respected, and all information will be kept confidential.

Duration: Approximately 40 to 50 minutes.

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time without any consequences. Please complete our quick survey at the following link: [SURVEY LINK]. Once you've filled out the survey, I will contact you to schedule the interview at a time convenient for you.

Alternatively, you can reach me at [Email id of interviewer]. Your insights will help in understanding the challenges faced during this process.

Thank you for your time and support!

If you have any questions or need further information, please feel free to contact me.

Warm regards,

[Interviewer name and Email id]